

Effect of Induction Delivery Time on Apgar Score in Lower Segment Cesarean Section Under Spinal Anesthesia

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ABSTRACT

We aimed to study the effect of induction delivery time on the Apgar score of the baby in patients undergoing lower segment caesarean section under spinal anesthesia. There are no proper guidelines available for the optimum induction to delivery time, but published literature informs that the average induction to delivery time is 10-20mins. There is popular belief that if the patient is given spinal anesthesia, the duration of induction delivery time has no effect on Apgar score of the baby. Many studies have already reported the effect of induction delivery time on Apgar score under general anesthesia; however, there are only a few studies available for the same under spinal anesthesia. Sixty term parturients undergoing lower segment caesarian section under spinal anesthesia during the study period were randomly selected. The time of induction, time of incision to skin, time of incision to uterus, time of delivery of baby and the Apgar score of the baby at 1min was recorded after giving spinal anesthesia. We allocated 60 patients under two groups of 30 each- Group A (Induction delivery time < 20min) and Group B (Induction delivery time > 20min). The mean induction delivery time (Group A: 14.3 ± 2.96 min; Group B: 22.79 ± 2.58 min) and the Apgar score (Group A: 8.13 ± 0.73; Group B: 6.67 ± 0.88) of both the groups were compared statistically [p value is less than 0.0001]. Here we concluded that induction delivery time is prolonged under spinal anesthesia there is a significant decrease in the Apgar score.

KEY WORDS: apgar score, cesarean section, induction time, spinal anesthesia

INTRODUCTION:

Obstetric anesthesia is a demanding subspecialty of anesthesiology and it requires special skills because two lives are involved. Although most patients undergoing cesarean section are young and healthy, still they represent a high risk group. Spinal Anesthesia was introduced by Bier in 1899, Tuffier did remarkably to make it popular and the technique achieved a widespread acceptance.^[1] By 1907, it was being used widely in almost all branches of surgery and obstetrics as well.^[1] The choice of anesthesia for cesarean section depends upon indication for operation, its urgency, patients and obstetrician preferences and the anesthesiologist. Either of the general and spinal anesthesia is not ideal for cesarean

section because each has advantages and risk to both mother and fetus.^[2,3] However the aim of anesthetist is to choose the method which is safest and most comfortable for the mother, least depressant to the newborn and which provides optimal working conditions for the obstetrician.^[4] The outcome of anesthesia either spinal or general depends upon the condition of the mother and more importantly effects on newborn.

Apgar score is the best parameter to assess the immediate condition of the baby.^[1,5] Apgar scoring is a numerical expression of the condition of the neonates on scale from 0-10. It is simple and a useful guide for neonatal well being and resuscitation. It has been observed that a prolonged induction delivery time is associated with a poor fetal outcome. Long skin incision to delivery time > 10min and uterine incision to delivery time > 3min are associated with fetal hypoxia and acidosis regardless of the type of anesthesia.^[7,8,9] The present research aimed to study the effect of induction delivery time on the Apgar

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score of the baby in patients undergoing lower segment caesarean section under spinal anesthesia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was carried out at Acharya Vinobha Bhave Rural Hospital, Sawangi (Meghe), Wardha during October 2014 to March 2015 after obtaining approval from institutional ethical committee. The study was performed on 60 healthy full term patients (as per criteria of American Society of Anesthesiologists) posted for elective lower segment caesarean section. The APGAR scores were recorded immediately after each delivery, and patients were divided into two groups of thirty patients in each group, Group A- Induction delivery time < 20 min and Group B- Induction delivery time > 20 min. Total 60 patients were included in the study and a written consent was taken from each patients. All patients in the study received spinal anesthesia.

Spinal anesthesia: Patient was placed in lateral or sitting position, space between 3rd and 4th lumbar spine was identified. After taking all aseptic measures lumbar puncture was done with 23 gauge Quinke's spinal needle and hyperbaric Bupivacaine 0.5%, 1.8 to 2.2 ml (7.5-12mg) was given. Immediately after injection of Bupivacaine patient was placed in supine position with wedge under right hip for left uterine displacement. Monitoring was done for the pulse, non invasive blood pressure (N.I.B.P), oxygen saturation, Electrocardiogram (ECG) and urinary output. Following was recorded during every caesarean section -Time of induction, time of incision to skin, time of incision of the uterus, time of delivery of baby.

In this study Apgar score of all 60 neonates were recorded at 1min after delivery of baby. Apgar score of each baby was compared with the standard Apgar score as shown in Table 1.

RESULTS:

We found if the induction delivery time was prolonged under spinal anesthesia, there was significant decrease in the Apgar score. The mean induction delivery time in Group A was 14.3±2.96 min and in Group B was 22.79 ±2.58 min as shown in Table 2. The mean Apgar score in Group A was 8.13 ±0.73 and in Group B was 6.67±0.88 as shown in Table 3.

The comparison of mean induction delivery time and mean Apgar score is shown graphically in graph 1 and 2 respectively.

Thus we observed that in group A when induction delivery time is less than 20 min the mean Apgar score was 8.13 ±0.73, but in group B where the induction delivery time was more than 20min the mean Apgar score was 6.67±0.88. Hence even under spinal anesthesia the Apgar score of the baby is affected by the induction delivery time.

DISCUSSION:

Delivery of baby by caesarean section has become increasingly common. However, choice of anesthetic technique remains controversial. As it is said earlier that no technique is ideal for caesarean sections, and both general and spinal anesthesia have certain advantages and disadvantages.^[1,2] Comparisons of the condition of neonates delivered by elective caesarean section under general and spinal anesthesia have demonstrated better clinical outcomes with regional anesthetic techniques.

There are different opinions about the ideal time at which the fetus should be delivered after induction of anesthesia. Barter was the first to emphasize that the parturient should be prepared and draped before induction of general anesthesia. Many researches have recommended that delivery is best completed 6 ± 8 minutes after induction of general anesthesia as nitrous oxide could cause neonatal depression by diffusion through the placenta. Datta et al studied the relationship of induction-to-delivery and uterine incision-to-delivery intervals to neonatal outcome and found out that, during general anesthesia, induction-to-delivery intervals of more than 8 minutes and uterine incision-to-delivery intervals of more than 3 minutes were associated with significantly more instances of neonatal acidosis (umbilical artery pH 7.31 versus 7.22) and a greater incidence of low 1-min Apgar scores (4% versus 73%). In the groups receiving spinal anesthesia, prolongation of uterine incision-to-delivery interval by more than 3 minutes was found to be the only important factor influencing fetal outcome, as determined by an increased acidosis (umbilical artery pH 7.30 versus 7.18) and by depressed Apgar scores (0% versus 62%).^[6]

Morgan described that long skin incision-to-delivery time more than 8 minutes and uterine-incision-to delivery time more than 180 seconds have been associated with fetal hypoxia and acidosis

Table 1: Recording of Apgar score.

APGAR Score	0	1	2
Heart rate	Absent	<100	>100
Respiratory Effort	Absent	Irregular	Good
Reflex irritability	No response	Grimace	Cough/ Sneeze
Appearance (color)	Blue or Pale	Body pink with blue Extremities	Completely Pink
Muscle tone	Flaccid	Good tone	Spontaneous Flexion

Table 2: Comparison of Induction Delivery Time between Group A and Group B.

Group	Group A	Group B	p value
Mean	14.30 ±2.96	22.79 ±2.58	
SD	2.96	2.58	p = 0.0001
SEM	0.54	0.48	

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Apgar Score (at 1 min) between Group A and Group B.

Group	Group A	Group B	p value
Mean	8.13±0.73	6.67±0.88	
SD	0.73	0.88	p = 0.0001
SEM	0.13	0.16	

regardless of the type of anesthesia.^[7] SK Kamat et al found that patients who received general anesthesia have a relatively high level of circulating catecholamines (response evoked by handling the uterus) causing a reduction in placental blood flow, thereby leading to acidosis, the effect of which occurs for prolonged time when uterine delivery interval increases.^[8,9]

Thus we observe that in the past studies the induction delivery time of more than 10 min under general anesthesia have poor fetal outcome. But there are no such clear guidelines under spinal anesthesia.

Many surgeons take long time to deliver the baby if the patient is under spinal anesthesia as they think it will not affect the Apgar score. But this is not true. In our study we found out that even under spinal anesthesia if the induction delivery time is prolonged (more than 20 min), then also there is lower Apgar score of the baby. This is due to decreased uteroplacental blood flow due to sympathetic block, and as the induction delivery interval is prolonged, this further jeopardizes the placental blood flow leading to poor neonatal outcome.

Graph 1: Comparison of mean induction delivery time (in min) in Group A and Group B.

Graph 2: Comparison of Mean Apgar score (at 1 min) in Group A and Group B.

CONCLUSION:

Under spinal anesthesia if the induction delivery time is prolonged, there is significant decrease in the Apgar score. The induction delivery time should be < 20min, so that there is better neonatal outcome. Here we conclude even under spinal anesthesia induction delivery time is an important factor, so the baby should be delivered within 20 min of induction of anesthesia.

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